

FUNDAMENTAL GROUPS IN CHAOTIC FLAT SPACE AND ITS RETRACTIONS

Authors : A. E. EL-AHMADY , M.ABU-SALEEM

Abstract : The purpose of this paper is to give a combinatorial characterization and also construct representations of the chaotic fundamental groups of the chaotic submanifolds of chaotic flat space by using some geometrical transformations. The chaotic homotopy groups of the limit folding for chaotic flat space are presented. The chaotic fundamental groups of some types of chaotic geodesics in chaotic flat space are deduced.

Keywords : Chaotic flat space; Chaotic folding; Chaotic retractions; Chaotic fundamental groups.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014